

ANALYSIS OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS

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Annotation. This in the article the sun from energy electronics elements from the help using electricity energy get, moreover electronics of the elements characteristics cause passed. Theoretical research and practical developments in the field of solar energy photoelectric converters have confirmed the possibility of high FIK in the conversion of radiation energy in photoelectric converters, and the main directions for achieving this goal are determined.

Key words: Photoelectric converters, electronvolt, free electron, illumination.

F autoelectric converters have a characteristic limit of 90% of their theoretical FIC at equilibrium temperatures of about 300-350 K and solar $T \approx 6000$ K. This shows that optimizing the structure and performance of converters aimed at reducing irreversible energy losses can actually increase the actual FIK to 50% and more (in laboratories, is now up to 40%).

The transformation of the generated energy when the inhomogeneous semiconductor structures of FEOs are exposed to solar radiation is called the photoelectric effect. based on

l The photon energy (eV) in long-wavelength radiation is determined by the following relationship:

$$h\nu = h \frac{c}{\lambda} = \frac{1,24}{\lambda};$$

where $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34}$ J·s – Planck's constant; $c = 2.997925 \times 10^8$ m/s – speed of light; λ – wavelength, μm .

Electronvolt is the energy required to move an electron between two points with a potential difference of 1 V.

$$1 \text{ eV} = 1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J.}$$

l_g Photons are absorbed in the material of the solar photovoltaic cell from the threshold wavelength:

$$l_g = 1.24 / \Delta E U;$$

where ΔYE is the forbidden area, characterized by the absence of levels, its width is different for different materials,

$$\Delta YE \approx (1...2) \text{ eV}.$$

Longer-wavelength radiation is not absorbed by semiconductors, so it is useless from a photoelectric conversion point of view.

Semiconductor devices for converting solar energy into electrical energy are known as solar photovoltaic cells.

Half conductive of materials Germanic *Ge* and silicon *Si* most important is considered Silicon DI Mendeleev Periodic IV group in the system to the elements includes, his valence 4 ha equal to Silicon atoms external electron to 4 electrons in the shell has [1, B.47].

Figure 1: Crystal lattice of pure silicon

When energy (heat or light) is applied, the interatomic bonds in the lattice lose electrons, creating positive charges. The non-electron space in the lattice is called a hole. A "hole" is an atom that has lost an electron, which causes holes to "move" as electrons move from hole to hole (the "holes" themselves do not move) [2, B.49].

If the semiconductor is not affected by an external electric field, holes and free electrons move randomly. If a semiconductor is placed in an electric field, the movement of holes and electrons will be ordered. The direction of movement of holes

from one atom to another corresponds to the direction of current through the semiconductor. Conductivity formed by the movement of holes is called holey or *r*-type conductivity. Conductivity created by the movement of electrons is called electronic or *p*-type conductivity. Thus, the conductivity of a semiconductor is determined by the movement of electrons in the field of conduction and electrons in the field of valence. But it is assumed that holes move in the valence field, not electrons. The conductivity of a semiconductor resulting from the breaking of valence bonds is called specific conductivity is called.

tetravalent *Si* silicon is alloyed with pentavalent *R* phosphorus, an excess electron is formed instead of an atomic site of the mixture (2 *a* - picture).

Figure 2. The crystal lattice of doped silicon:

a - phosphorus with *b* - there is with

Free electrons to the body bringer to mixtures donor is called. In this case silicon electron conductive semiconductor or of *p*-type is called a semiconductor of *p*-type in a semiconductor conductivity only electrons with harvest is done.

Diffusion tends to create a flow of electrons from the *n*-area to the *p*-area, while the field of the charged layer, on the contrary, tries to return electrons to the *n*-area. Similarly, the *np* area at the transition from *p*- to *n*-area counteracts the diffusion of holes. After a certain time, an equilibrium is formed. As a result of the accumulation of charges, on both sides of the transition, an electric field of opposite sign is created, free electrons and holes are formed as a result of the difference in concentration, which balances the diffusion. As a result, the Fermi level is under constant potential. Forbidden region ΔYE is present in the entire material, and

potential jumps between the energies of the conduction band and the valence band are formed.

The contact potential difference created at the junction resists the passage of the main charge carriers, that is, the passage of electrons by *the p*- layer, but allows non-main charge carriers to pass without resistance in the opposite direction.

np -transitions makes it possible to generate photoelectric driving force (photoelectric driving force) when FEO is irradiated with solar light.

Electron-hole pairs formed by light in both layers of the FEO are separated at *the np* -junction: non-major carriers (electrons) pass freely through the transition, while major carriers (holes) will hold. Thus, both in *the np* -transition under the influence of solar radiation in the direction of unbalanced non-main charge carriers (photoelectrons and photoholes necessary for FEO' operation) current flows.

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